

Labour Regulations And Operational Performance Of Small And Medium Enterprises: A Close Look Into Employment Equity Amendments In South Africa

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 22, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: November 23, 2022</p>	<p><i>Small and medium companies (SMEs) play an essential role in bringing sustainable economic development and remains a pipedream to various countries. However, the rapid closure and decline of SMEs take a centre stage amongst the contributors to the shrinkage of South African economy. As such, the quest for economic growth has prompted the need for closely look at impact of labour regulations on operational performance of SMEs. The key purpose of the paper is to examine the impact of labour regulations on operational performance of SMEs with specific attention given to employment equity amendments in South Africa. While labour policies are promulgated to attain predetermined goals, the quest to accomplish those goals should not be an impediment to operational performance of SMEs. In this paper, the quantitative research approach and descriptive research design were utilised. The sample for this study was 226 SMEs in South Africa. It was evident from the results of this paper that the amendments to employment equity legislation were not emancipating SMEs, but rather impeding their operational performance. The employment equity amendments caused a reshuffling of the current workforce instead of creating jobs. This study served as a guide in decision-making and provide advice related to the impact employment equity amendments on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa. The management of SMEs ought to constructively engage with the government and labour to reveal the trade-offs that are inclusive and sustainable for all parties. A demarcation line needs to be drawn between the economic interests and political interests, and reform these amendments for the sake of reviving the whole economy.</i></p>
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Introduction

Emerging economies like South Africa promulgate labour regulations to achieve different goals in the labour market. Nevertheless, some labour regulations are seen to be infused with an array of complex dilemmas and paradoxes which prompted the different stakeholders to continuously examine the trade-offs between the government goals and operational performance of SMEs (Ranchhod & Daniels, 2021; Sithole, 2021). The SMEs are required to remain competitive at national and global levels (Adewumi, 2020). According to Bongani (2020), the company value is mostly based on its operational performance. It is imperative to note that for the company to gain greater value, an equivalent increase in operational performance should be achieved. The current paper focuses on examining the impact of the labour regulations on the operational performance of SMEs with particular attention given to employment equity amendments in South Africa. The amendments to the principal Employment Equity Act No. 55 of 1998 are within the law, namely Employment Equity Amendment Act No. 47 of 2013 (EEAA) (Ebrahim, 2018). The reforms in the form of amendments to employment equity are radical in order to accomplish quick results. As such, those reforms are perceived as not aimed at improving the regulatory quality. Over the past few years, employment equity amendments have been subjected to wholly philosophically-based debates and contradictions. Whilst some views are positive, others view them as negative. Some organisations view them as legal responsibility (Espí, Francis & Valodia, 2019), some view them as costs (Mayer, Oosthuizen, & Tonelli, 2019), some view them as mechanisms to endorse ethical behavior (Kanjere & Ngwakwe, 2018) and some view them as a way of making money through tenders (Landman & O'Clery, 2020). Such substantial mixed views and arguments prompted the researcher to empirically examine the impact of employment equity amendments on operational performance. Although scholars have researched the principal employment equity (Landman & O'Clery, 2020; Mayer, Oosthuizen, & Tonelli, 2019; Espí, Francis & Valodia, 2019; Kanjere & Ngwakwe, 2018), none of them has so far researched on the new amendments to employment equity in relation to operational performance. There is a lacuna in literature. While the introduction of the amendments can lower labour imbalances, the operational performance of companies is overlooked, in particular that of still growing small and medium companies. According to

Oosthuizen and Mayer (2019), the two key objectives of the Employment Equity Act (EEA) are: firstly, to eradicate unfair discrimination; and secondly, to execute measures of affirmative action. The first objective applies to all employers, whereas the second objective applies only to designated employers that are obliged to take corrective steps to implement measures of affirmative action. In this paper, a designated employer refers to the employer who employs 50 employees and above. It is crucial to note that complying with the amendments to employment equity while optimally realising an increase in operational performance is a challenge for many organisations.

Research problem

The universal concern about tenacious stagnation and amplified dramatic economic downfall associated with acute poverty and unemployment levels has prompted a look for the root cause of the dilemma and search for mechanisms which would promote the revamping of economic activities in various economies. SMEs play an integral role in the South African economy as they contribute to over 50% of newly created jobs (Worku 2016). However, due to growth stagnation, some face closure as they fail to cope with amended legislation, in particular the Employment Equity amendment legislation. The situation has been further deepened by the emergence of COVID-19 pandemic which pressed down SMEs that attempting to maneuver the difficulties associated with the demands of employment equity amendments (Akpan, Udoh & Adebisi, 2022; Adam & Alarifi, 2021). It is worrisome that few to no SMEs have succeeded in developing into big companies due to these amendments to legislation. SMEs find it too difficult or costly to be in compliance with the regulations due to the fact that they are not able to spread the costs across a wide base, as larger companies are able to do (Makwara, 2019; Masama, 2018).

The paper sought to accomplish the following objectives:

- To establish the influence of equal pay-for-equal work on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To determine the effect of extension of discriminatory grounds on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To examine the impact of removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To evaluate the effect of increased fines on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To assess the influence of removal of occupational categories on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To determine the influence of consequences of failing to comply with Director-General on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To examine the effect of burden of proof on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To establish the impact of annual reporting on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To determine the influence of enforcement procedures on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To evaluate the effect of sexual harassment handled by CCMA on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To determine the influence of increment of total annual turnover threshold on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To establish the effect of assessments of regional and national demographics on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.
- To evaluate the effect of psychometric tests assessments on operational performance of SMEs in South Africa.

Literature Review

Companies within the South African economy are grouped into three categories: by annual revenue, by total assets (excluding fixed assets) and by number of employees (Frans, Elize & Hendrik 2014). According to Frans et al. (2014), in South Africa, a small organisation has not more than 50 employees and medium organisation has between 51 to 200 employees. Operational performance is seen as a key dimension of overall business performance that focuses on the effectiveness of the business (Odoom 2016). Small and medium organisations seek to improve operational performance. Due to the fact that the amendments only consider victims of apartheid or people who become citizens by naturalisation, foreign national persons or persons who became citizens later than 27 April 1994 are no longer considered for affirmative action target purposes. Should staff appointments before this amendment constitute employees who became citizens of South Africa after the democracy or foreign national person, meeting the targets of affirmative action is negatively affected (Sesant, 2017; Musetsho, Isaac & Dobrin, 2021). Most people who received permanent residency and some foreign nationals are experienced and skilled in particular critical positions and fields. Hence, replacing them with partially experienced people from designated groups to meet affirmative action targets is affecting productivity (Nene, 2021; Ogujiuba, Boshoff, Agholor & Olamide, 2020). Employers are required to immediately abide by

the employment equity amendments or risk paying huge penalties and strict mechanisms of enforcement. This endangers productivity as they rush to employ semi-skilled employees at the expense of qualified permanent residency employees, with the aim of meeting affirmative action targets. There is no transitional time-frame given for SMEs to comply with the amendments.

The chance to make an objection to a compliance order is now removed in new amendment (Booyesen & Nkomo, 2014). Making an appeal on labour inspector's compliance order is repealed, according to section 37(1). This may stifle the growth of small and mediums businesses whereby they are forced to comply without taking into consideration the viability of the businesses' operations. While carrying out things better improves organisation's financial performance, conducting things well increases revenue. Some compliance orders cause inflexibility, increase costs to the organisation, retard speed of production, as well as cause poor quality of goods and/or services (Abrahams, 2019). This normally takes place when the labour inspector orders the employer, for instance, to have a race that is not readily and suitably available. This may counter the innovation of products and services since qualified personnel may be overlooked as the SMEs seek to comply with orders through focusing on hiring employees based on race, gender and disability (Webster & Francis, 2019). For SMEs to realise their potential, they need to be spared from complying with all orders. Some internal processes of production in SMEs are so sophisticated such that they demand experts, not just hiring candidates because of their designated groups. Operational cycle durations of production may be prolonged as a result of some unbearable orders, hence it is necessary to be careful when such orders are sanctioned. Peyper (2017) posits that failure to adapt to the new environment of the amended Employment Equity Act is likely to lead to higher prosecutions as provisions of affirmative action are breached. However, some companies are resorting to splitting into divisions that bear different names so that they fall below the prescribed thresholds as a strategy to avoid the demands of the new amendments.

The amendments to Employment Equity Legislation

Any designated employer should ensure that discrimination is eliminated, and that qualified and suitable employees from previously disadvantaged groups are afforded the same chances of employment prospects and that all categories have reasonable representations across job levels (Mkhize & Mgcotyelwa-Ntoni, 2019; Heerden, 2015). A remarkable number of amendments were made (Booyesen & Nkomo, 2014), key amendments are being: i) Enforcement procedures (amendments to sections 39 and 40)- Compliance orders are now issued by the labour inspector without initially waiting to receive a written undertaking from the employer. Section 36 that dealt with employers' undertaking to abide with the request of the labour inspector is deleted. ii) Only apartheid victims to benefit- Amendments to the 'designated groups' definition in terms of Chapter III state that affirmative action beneficiaries are now only restricted to women, people with disability and black people who were citizens of South Africa prior to the democratic era (before 27 April 1994) or who would have received the citizen entitlement but were deprived by apartheid policies, or who are South Africa by descent or birth. iii) Increased fines (Amendments to sections 59, 61 and Schedule 1)- The maximum fine for breach of the Act is now increased threefold. Should the revenue be higher than a fine, a fine range which varies from 2%-10% of the turnover is charged, depending on the offence committed for failure to abide by the provisions of the affirmative action within the Act (Peyper, 2017; Abrahams, 2019).

iv) Annual reports (Amendments to sub-section 21(1) and (4A)) - In the past, annual reports were required to be submitted by designated employers that had more than 150 employees, whilst those designated employers who have lower than 150 staff were obliged to submit in the second year. However, the new amendment now requires all designated employers to submit employment equity reports annually. v) The burden of proof (Amendment to section 11)- Now, the amendment act forms two facets of 'burden of proof', by either the employee or employer. Firstly, in terms of section 11(1), the burden to prove lie in the hands of the employer where the ground of unfair discrimination is listed in section 6(1) and proof should be based on a balance of probability. Secondly, in terms of section 11(2), the burden to prove shifts to the employee (complainant), where the unfair discrimination lies on arbitrary grounds (not listed ground) and should be proven based on a balance of probabilities. vi) CCMA's jurisdiction (Amendment of Section 10)- Now, all matters that concern sexual harassment of all employees irrespective of their earning thresholds, or issues related to unfair discrimination in which the earnings threshold of employees involved falls below R205 433.30 prescribed in section 6(3) of the BCEA, or by consent of both parties, matters of unfair discrimination of employees who have higher earnings are dealt with under the jurisdiction of CCMA where arbitration for the dispute can be handled in terms of Section 10(6) after conciliation (Heerden, 2015).

vii) Psychometric tests- Employers that use psychometric tests should make sure that the tests have the approval and certifications of the Health Professions Council of South Africa (HPCSA). vii) Inclusion of Equal treatment ('equal pay for equal work or work of equal value')- The insertion of the new section 6 (4) and section 6(5) explicitly focuses on the concept of equal treatment, which requires more than the issue of 'equal work for equal pay'. viii) Discriminatory grounds extended – Section 6(1) of the Amendment Act expands the grounds of unfair discrimination. The expansion of the meaning of unfair discrimination prohibits unfair discrimination on any other arbitrary grounds. ix) Total annual turnover threshold (Amendments to schedule 4) - Amendments to section 64A increases the annual threshold that is required to be exceeded for the employer to fall under the classification of 'designated employer'. x) Occupational categories excluded- Occupational levels are now set as points of reference. Occupational categories were removed.

xi) Assessment of compliance- Regulations that deal with compliance assessment where issues such as economically active populations of regional and national levels are taken into consideration now falls under the hands of the Minister of Labour. xii) Reports to the Director General (Amendments to section 21)- This amendment gives a time-frame of when designated employers are expected to submit reports to the Department of Labour's Director General (DG). xiii) Consequences of failing to comply with Director General (Amendment to section 45)- An amendment to section 45 makes an extension where section 45(1)(a) and (b) is now included. The extension provides specific action taken by the Director General in the event of failure by the employer to abide by a requisition made by Director-General in accordance with section 43(2) or according to section 44(b) recommendation made by the Director-General.

The concept of operational performance

Operational performance is seen as performance that is influenced directly by behavioural actions from the workforce of the company. It is divided into sub-dimensions, namely product quality, customer satisfaction, process and product innovation, market building, employee satisfaction, network building and organisational building (Visnjic, Wiengarten & Neely 2016). Furthermore, the list above is not exhaustive as the performance dimensions can be contextualised to address the problem since the effectiveness comes from the problem-driven construct. The lower-level performance is usually shown by poor operations. Operational performance indicators are revealed through firm productivity and product quality. Typical operating performance measurements can be innovation, sales, quality of service, productivity and quality of production (Wang, Senaratne & Rafiq 2015). Most operational performances can be easily broken down in numbers, for instance number of customer complaints, quantity of new developed products and number of products produced (Ayob, Ramlee & Rahman 2015). The measures of operations encompass variables that present the manner in which the organisation is performing on non-financial aspects (Dubey, Gunasekaran & Chakrabarty, 2015). These aspects incorporate customer satisfaction, market share and the transformation in intangible assets, for instance patents. The efficiency ratios, market-based ratios, innovation practices and survival measures are incorporated in measuring operational performance. For this study, innovation, productivity and quality of goods and services are the measures of operational performance.

The Neo-institutional theory

The Neo-institutional theory - According to Jain, Horwitz and Wilkin (2012), the neo-institutional theory focuses on shaping the actions of the organisation to align with external social forces. These forces influence the manner in which operations of certain functions are conducted, thereby becoming institutionalised within the organisation. These external forces impact on the performance of the business. In accordance with neo-institutional theory, the key assumption is that organisations want to prove legitimacy to the external world (Geldenhuys, 2016). In relation to this study, SMEs seek to abide by the amendments to Employment Equity regardless of the how their businesses are performing. Ignorance to heeding this law's demands results in small and medium organizations fined hefty penalties that in turn affect operational performance in terms of finances. Primary mechanisms that affect organisations' actions are subdivided into three: regulatory forces, normative forces and mimetic forces (Mathapelo, 2014). Firstly, the regulative forces, are forces connected to certain government rules and laws. The Neo-institutional theory is general in nature in the sense that it is not specific to a particular law. Hence, this paper narrowly and clearly expands the existing Institutional theory to align with Employment Equity amendments by employing a deductive approach which is grounded in the empirical testing of critical incidents that come as a result of the execution of amendments to employment equity. In this case, the theory can be expanded to clearly align with the Employment Equity Amendment Act.

Method

Research approach and design

This study adopted the descriptive research design. The descriptive research design can effectively address the research problem relating to the impact of employment equity implementation on the operational performance in South Africa. Descriptive research address types of the research questions that seek examine the relationship between employment equity amendments and operational performance (Kothari,2020). This study utilised a quantitative approach. A quantitative research approach gave the quantitative relationships and examined the empirical analysis between employment equity amendments and operational performance in a mathematically expressed manner. For this study, the target population constituted all 550 industrial relations representatives in SMEs across all industries in South Africa. In this study, the number of employees was used to determine whether or not the employer qualifies to be a designated employer. In terms of Employment Equity Amendments Act, the employer should have at least 50 employees and above to qualify to be a designated employer.

Sampling procedure and sample size

Probability sampling was utilised. A simple random sampling technique was employed to select a sample in which computer generated random numbers was utilised in selecting the sample. In accordance with a sample size table developed by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), a sample size of 226 should be utilised for a target population consisting of 550 elements/units. Computer-generated random numbers was utilised in selecting the sample. For this study, the primary data was collected utilising structured close-ended questionnaires. The mail survey utilised a structured questionnaire. The 'five-point Likert scale' was utilised for each of the questions that was asked (strongly agree, agree neutral, disagree and strongly disagree). The closed-ended questionnaire responses was coded in a data set form in which both inferential and descriptive statistics was utilised for analysis. Then the data was analysed utilising the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 for Windows by employing relevant statistical tests.

Results and Discussion

In terms of reliability testing, the suitable test for this paper was the internal consistency reliability test which was performed by computing Cronbach's alpha. The paper calculated 17 variables using Cronbach's alpha. The minimum accepted value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.6, especially for descriptive research. The coefficient alpha of *equal pay-for-equal work* was 0.93. The coefficient alpha of *extension of discriminatory grounds* was 0.71. A Coefficient alpha of 0.65 was obtained for *removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups*. *Increased fines* scored a coefficient alpha of 0.86. The coefficient alpha of *removal of occupational categories* was 0.88. A coefficient alpha of 0.97 was obtained for *consequences of failing to comply with the Director-General*. The coefficient alpha of *burden of proof* is 0.95. A coefficient alpha of 0.93 was obtained for *annual reporting*. The coefficient alpha of *enforcement procedures* was 0.72. A coefficient alpha of 0.86 was obtained for *sexual harassment handled by CCMA*. The coefficient alpha of *increment of total annual turnover threshold* was 0.93. The coefficient alpha of *assessments of compliance* was 0.73. The coefficient alpha of *operational performance* was 0.76. One may conclude that the reliability coefficient accomplished by all constructs is suitable as they are over 0.60, hence reflecting questionnaire stability and consistency (Hair, Samuel & Babin 2003).

The biographical data of the respondents utilised for the collection of primary data were obtained. To ascertain that the respondents included in the study were relevant, the study asked them for some demographic information. The background information that relates to the number of employees that a company has, the sector to which the companies belong, occupation of the respondents, the level which the occupation falls under, highest level of education, gender, age bracket and race of the respondents were analysed. The findings of this study showed that the bulk of the industrial relations representatives (63.38%) who participated in this research were males. The outcomes of this study were not aligned with the gender distribution since females constitute two-thirds of the entire population in South Africa. The ideal threshold ratio must be 1:2, meaning there must be one male for every two females, not the other way round. These results are supported by Ainin, Parveen, Moghavvemi, Jaafar and Shuib (2015) who identify that males dominate top management of SMEs. Moreover, this may imply that males are good in the adoption of the industrial relations positions of SMEs. The results of this study showed that a majority of SMEs that participated in this study had between 51 to 150 employees. In terms of the industry in which the SMEs fall, the results of the study indicated that the manufacturing industry; construction industry; and repair services, motor trade and retail industry were the main sectors that participated in this research. The findings also indicate that most respondents (69.44%) had degrees. This clearly indicates

that the respondents were reasonably educated to grasp matters pertaining to the impact of amendments to employment equity legislation on operational performance. This implies that most SMEs hired well-trained candidates who have sufficient capabilities to administer and handle the industrial relations matters, in particular the amendments to employment equity legislation, without much difficulty.

The findings revealed that the predominant age group of the respondents (industrial relations representatives) who participated in this research was between 35 to 50 years. This reflects that the respondents were middle aged and at these ages, it is mostly likely that they gave informed responses that are relevant to this research study. This is a mature, economically active group which is knowledgeable about current situations in the environment they are working in. This also signifies that the respondents that participated in this research were not minors. For this reason, the researcher developed confidence on the collected data as the bulk of the respondents and they were mature enough to provide relevant information. Hence it was the right age group that one can freely participate with and provide informed responses to the questions. The findings conform with the views of Asah, Fatoki and Rungani (2015), asserting that the input that the person exerts is directly proportional to the age of the individual. One could conclude that given the age bracket of the respondents, the information provided was reliable.

Table 1: Descriptive analysis

Statement	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I perceive that the equal pay-for-equal work is causing an increase in job losses.	5	3.45	.778
Loss of foreign skilled employees lowers our production.	5	3.73	.750
We spend a lot of time dealing with a multitude of issues of discrimination at our within the past three years.	5	3.66	.803
Any penalty in the new amendments to employment equity that may be fined is likely to lead to the shut down of our company.	5	3.75	.760
The increase in the number of reports adds an administration burden.	5	3.73	.768
The removal of a chance to object to some compliances causes stunted growth to our business and some others order suppress innovation.	5	3.75	.795
The removal of occupational categories reduces time wasted in scrutinising job levels in the company.	5	3.86	.561
We ensure that the employment agency we deal with has psychometric tests registered, approved and certified by the Health Professions Council of South Africa (HPCSA)	5	3.75	.641
It is good to us that an employee should prove to us that we have discriminated against them based on arbitrary grounds	5	3.89	.718
The enforcement procedures are too tight for us.	5	3.93	.631
Some employees are silently lodging their disputes at the CCMA without management's knowledge.	5	3.88	.604
The increment of total annual turnover threshold does not affect our operational performance.	5	3.89	.614
We do not have any confusion in respect of the implementation of regional and national demographics	5	2.45	.959
Our production decreased significantly in the past 3 years.	5	3.77	.755
We need much innovation to be competitive on the global market.	5	3.75	.662

We strive to produce products and services of high quality	5	3.88	.526
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The results in Table 1 clearly point to respondents seeing themselves shutting down their companies if they receive any penalty in terms of the new amendments to employment equity. This is supported by a mean score of 3.75. From a practical organisational point of view, the respondents indicated that the increase in the number of reports adds an administration burden, as indicated by a mean score of 3.73. On the other related statement, the respondents affirmed that the removal of a chance to object to some compliances caused stunted growth to their businesses and some others suppress innovation. This is shown by a mean score of 3.75. It is interesting to note that the respondents believed that the removal of occupational categories reduces time wasted in scrutinising job levels in the company. This is reported by a mean score of 3.86. The respondents took a tentative position when asked if the equal pay equal work is causing an increase in job losses, as indicated by a mean score of 3.45. Further reinforcement was affirmed as respondents reported that they spent a lot of time dealing with a multitude of issues of discrimination at their companies within the past three years, as supported by a mean score of 3.66. The respondents took a tentative position when asked whether they use psychometric tests when selecting the right candidate for the job, as shown by a mean score of 3.40. These findings imply that SMEs utilise psychometric tests for critical jobs where all the requisites are conducted by specialised employment agencies. In terms of burden of proof, the respondents confirmed that it is good to them that an employee should prove to them that they have discriminated against them based on arbitrary grounds. This is indicated by a mean score of 3.89. In the same vein, the respondents felt that the enforcement procedures are too tight for them, as reported by a mean score of 3.93. As evident in Table 1, the respondents indicated that some employees are silently lodging their disputes at the CCMA without management's knowledge. This is confirmed by a mean score of 3.88. On another related statement in Table 1, the respondents disagreed that they do not have any confusion in respect of the implementation of regional and national demographics, as revealed by a mean score of 2.45. In respect of operational performance, the respondents affirmed that they need much innovation in order to be competitive on the global market as supported by a mean score of 3.75. On the other statement in Table 1, the respondents indicated that their production decreased significantly in the past 3 years, as shown by a mean score of 3.77. The respondents confirmed that they strive to produce products and services of high quality, as reported by a mean score of 3.88.

Table 2: Model summary - employment equity amendments and operational performance.

Model	R	Adjusted R ²
1	.953 ^a	.885
Predictors: (Constant) EEAA (equal pay-for-equal work; extension of discriminatory grounds; removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups; increased fines; removal of occupational categories; consequences of failing to comply with Director-General; burden of proof; annual reporting; enforcement procedures; sexual harassment handled by CCMA; increment of total annual turnover threshold; assessments of regional and national demographics and psychometric tests)		

As illustrated by the regression equation in Table 2, the employment equity amendment legislation has a significant relationship with operational performance. This was indicated by the correlation value of 0.953, which is a considered a significant relationship because the value falls above 0.70 (Pallant 2011). The adjusted R2 reflects that 88.5% (0.885) of the operational performance could be explained by the independent variables. Table 3 below reports on analysis of value test results.

Table 3: ANOVA Test Results

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	.789	14	9.789	40.075	.000
	Residual	2.769	57	.244		
	Total	3.558	71			

- Dependent variable: Operational performance
- Predictors: (Constant) EEAA (equal pay-for-equal work; extension of discriminatory grounds; removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups; increased fines; removal of occupational categories; consequences of failing to comply with Director-General; burden of proof; annual reporting; enforcement procedures; sexual harassment handled by CCMA; increment of total annual turnover threshold; and assessments of regional and national demographics and psychometric tests)

Critical F= 2.51304

The test in Table 3 reflects a statistically significant F calculated value of 40.075, which is above the minimum critical F value 2.51304. This implies that the generated regression equation by this study perfectly and significantly predicts the dependent variable. This is also corroborated by a p-value in which $p=0.000<0.05$. This means that the p-value (0.000) reported was lower than the conventional probability of 0.05 significance level. The outcomes of the test depict that the adopted regression equation in this study is of good fit, hence it is suitable to utilise to predict the operational performance based on the amendments of employment equity legislation reviewed in this study. Table 4 covers the coefficients of both independent (employment equity amendments) and dependent (operational performance) sub-variables.

Table 4: Coefficients

Model (Independent Variables)	Unstandardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B		
Constant	.827		.000
Equal pay-for-equal work	.701		.000
Extension of discriminatory grounds	.627		.001
Removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups	-.849		.002
Increased fines	-.652		.002
Removal of occupational categories	.197		.631
Consequences of failing to comply with Director-General	-.515		.025
Burden of proof	-.557		.026
Annual reporting	-.682		.018
Enforcement procedures	-.701		.001
Sexual harassment handled by CCMA	.203		.253
Increment of total annual turnover threshold	.054		.482
Assessments of regional and national demographics	-.761		.000
Psychological tests	.342		.372

a. Dependent Variable: Operational Performance

As observed in Table 4, the coefficient value of *equal pay-for-equal work* was 0.701. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could increase by 70.1%, given that there is 100% progress of *equal pay-for-equal work*. The statistical significance ($0.000<0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable ('equal pay-for-equal work') makes a significant and positive contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). In relation to Table 4, the coefficient value of *extension of discriminatory grounds* was -0.627. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could decrease by 62.7%, given that there is 100% progress of *extension of discriminatory grounds*. The statistical significance ($0.001<0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable ('extension of discriminatory grounds') makes a relatively significant and negative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). According to Table 4, the coefficient value of *removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups* was -0.849. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could decrease by 84.9%, given that there is 100% progress of *removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups*. The statistical significance ($0.002<0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable ('removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups') makes a highly significant and negative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). According to Table 4, the coefficient value of *increased fines* was -0.652. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant of, operational performance could decrease by 65.2%, given that there is 100% progress of *increased fines*. The statistical significance ($0.002<0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable ('increased fines') makes a relatively significant and negative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance).

As reflected in Table 4, the coefficient value of *removal of occupational categories* was 0.197. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could increase by 19.7%, given that there is 100% progress of *removal of occupational categories*. The statistical significance ($0.631>0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable *removal of occupational categories* makes an insignificant and positive

contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). In relation to Table 4, the coefficient value of *consequences of failing to comply with the Director-General* was -0.515. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could decrease by 51.5%, given that there is 100% progress of *consequences of failing to comply with the Director-General*. The statistical significance ($0.025 < 0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable ('consequences of failing to comply with the Director-General') makes a relatively significant and negative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). According to Table 4, the coefficient value of *burden of proof* was -0.557. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could decrease by 55.7%, given that there is 100% progress of *burden of proof*. The statistical significance ($0.026 < 0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable ('burden of proof') makes a relatively significant and negative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). In accordance with the analysis in Table 4, the coefficient value of *annual reporting* was -0.682. This entails that all things being equal, operational performance could decrease by 68.2%, given that there is 100% consideration of *annual reporting*. The statistical significance ($0.018 < 0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable ('annual reporting') makes a relatively significant and negative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance).

Table 4 illustrates that the coefficient value of *enforcement procedures* was -0.701. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could decrease by 70.1%, given that there is 100% progress of *enforcement procedures*. The statistical significance ($0.001 < 0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable (enforcement procedures) makes a significant and negative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). Table 4 shows that the coefficient value of *sexual harassment handled by CCMA* was 0.203. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could increase by 20.3%, given that there is 100% progress of *sexual harassment handled by CCMA*. The statistical significance ($0.253 > 0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable ('sexual harassment handled by CCMA') makes an insignificant and positive contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). On Table 4, the coefficient value of *increment of total annual turnover threshold* was 0.054. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could increase by 5.4%, given that there is 100% progress of *increment of total annual turnover threshold*. The statistical significance ($0.482 > 0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable (increment of total annual turnover threshold) makes an insignificant and positive contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). Table 4 reveals that the coefficient value of *assessments of compliance* (regional and national demographics) was -0.761. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could decrease by 76.1%, given that there is 100% progress of *assessments of compliance* (regional and national demographics). The statistical significance ($0.000 < 0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable *assessments of regional and national demographics* make a significant and negative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). On Table 4, the coefficient value of *psychological tests* was 0.342. This entails that when other independent variables are held constant, operational performance could increase by 34.2%, given that there is 100% progress of *psychological tests*. The statistical significance ($0.372 > 0.05$) means that the sub-independent variable (psychological tests) makes an insignificant and positive contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable (operational performance). The following sub-section reports the results of the correlation analysis.

Discussion

The results of the study indicated that the labour regulations in the form of new employment equity amendment legislation have a strong impact on operational performance of SMEs. Eniola and Entebang (2015) focused their study on government policy and SME performance in South Africa. Their results espoused that government policy has a great influence on SME competitiveness and growth. The finding of the study indicated that *equal pay-for-equal work* and *removal of occupational categories* positively affect operational performance. Regarding equal pay and gender equity, Conley and Page (2018) conducted a study in the United Kingdom, the results of which revealed that an over-reliance on legislation for organisations to implement equal pay at the workplace has caused government not to move from adversarial legislative forms to more relaxed responsive regulative forms of pay equality. The study finding also revealed that *extension of discriminatory grounds*, *removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups*, *increased fines*, *consequences of failing to comply with the Director general*, *burden of proof*, *annual reporting*, *enforcement procedures* and *assessments of regional and national demographics* have adverse impact on operational performance. This is confirmed by the findings of a study on the challenges faced by SMEs conducted by Chimucheka and Mandipaka (2015), which revealed that poor government regulations and policies are key impediments to the growth of SMEs. The outcomes of the study indicated that *psychometric tests*, *sexual harassment handled by CCMA* and *increment of total annual turnover*

threshold do not affect the operational performance of small and medium organisations. The negative impact of *removal of non-SA citizens from the designated groups* on operational performance is attributed to the removal of competent employees who are productive and who assist in delivering a service or creating a product. If the product or service is poor and is not selling, the organisation will be in danger of closing down. This is confirmed by a study carried out by Worku (2016) which focused on barriers to SME growth in the Vaal Triangle in South Africa. The surveyed sample of 303 employees revealed that inadequate skills affect the viability of SMEs.

The study established that there is a correlation between the removal of non-South African citizens from designated groups and the operational performance of SMEs, which was negative. This negative relationship entails that an increase in the removal of non-South African citizens in employment would decrease operational performance. This finding is in line with a study carried out by Ngcobo and Sukdeo (2015) revealed that government laws and policies are claiming unrealistic, burdensome and complex demands which makes it difficult for SMCs to expand. The study concluded that there is a negative and significant correlation between the extension of discriminatory grounds and the operational performance of SMEs. The negative linkage implies that an increase in the exercise of 'extension of the discriminatory grounds' would decrease operational performance. These results contradicted with the findings of research conducted by Burger et al. (2016) in South Africa, which revealed that the continuous fall in black-white discrimination is credited to the permanent legislative effect, not a mere business cycle dividend. The study concluded that there is a weak and negative correlation between increased fines and the operational performance of small and medium companies. The inverse relationship entails that an improvement in the application of the increased fines would diminish operational performance.

The study established that there is a negative and strong correlation between amendments to consequences of failing to comply with the Director General and the financial performance of SMCs. This finding is in line with a study carried out by SBP in 2013 indicated that small and medium companies complained about the harsh labour regulations (SBP, 2013). The inverse relationship entails that an improvement in the application of the *consequences of failing to comply with Director General* would decrease the financial performance of SMCs. The study established that there is a strong and negative correlation between amendments to consequences of failing to comply with the Director General and the operational performance of SMCs. The negative relationship implies that an improvement in the application of the *consequences of failing to comply with the Director General* would decrease operational performance.

Conclusion

The impact of labour regulations in the form of employment equity amendments on the operational performance of SMEs has been established hence the primary objective of this study was accomplished. It was evident from the results of this study that the labour regulations in the form of amendments to employment equity legislation have not emancipated SMEs, but rather impeded their business performance. With this study, organizations can be able to identify which amendments to employment equity legislation have an impact on the operational performance of SMEs in South Africa. Even large companies can also gain insights from the results of this research and can apply some of the suggested recommendations. The research also helps the government, especially the Employment Equity Commission and Department of Labour, as to which amendments to employment equity legislation they must revise in order to rescue battling SMEs.

Recommendations

The SMEs and government should strike a balance and be sensitive in executing the implementation of measures of amendment of employment equity legislation in order to mutually stimulate operational performance and afford designated people to benefit from the measures within the legislation. Since data was collected from SMEs registered, this may hence not accurately represent all the SMEs in the whole of South Africa. The main limitation of the paper is that it narrowly focuses on registered SMEs, therefore precluding the generalisation of the findings to informal SMEs in South Africa. The study is restricted to SMEs only. As such, this study ignores the plight of large companies that might be facing similar predicaments. For future studies, it would be useful to study the impact of the amendments to employment equity legislation on the business performance of large companies.

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